

WAVE-BREAKING EFFECTS IN RADAR SIGNATURES FROM 2-DIMENSIONAL MODELLING OF THE HI-RES-1 RIP FEATURE

S. R. Chubb, A. L. Cooper, R. A. Fusina, R. W. Jansen
Remote Sensing Division

Naval Research Laboratory Washington, D. C. 20375-5351, U. S. A.

Telephone: 202.767.5270, FAX: 202.767.3303, EMAIL: chubb@ccf.nrl.navy.mil

Abstract -- Full-spectral modelling of a two-dimensional current structure is used to understand the role of wave-current interaction and wave-breaking (WB) effects in the Radar Signatures of the Rip-like sub-mesoscale feature that were observed during the First High Resolution Remote Sensing (HI-RES-1) experiment. It is found that the large variations in radar cross-section (RCS) in the neighborhood of the cusp-like features within the Rip can be reproduced with or without incorporation of wave-breaking (WB) effects. However, when WB effects are not included, consistent with previous models that have used 1-dimensional current structures, in regions away from these cusp-like structures, the composite scatterer (CB) model significantly underpredicts the magnitude of the signature. As a consequence, somewhat surprisingly, within the Rip, the CB model *over-predicts* the magnitude of the cusp signature relative to the signature from the Rip in non-cusp-like regions. By including WB effects, this deficiency is overcome, and good agreement is obtained. The resulting agreement occurs when the WB effect is based on an estimate of the local critical crest acceleration $\Omega_c = 0.4 g$ ($g = 9.8 \text{ m/s}^2$) that accompanies the onset of wave-breaking. This value for Ω_c is in good agreement with independently measured values obtained in wave-tank and field experiments. Incorporation of WB effects also eliminates a non-physical dependence on look-angle that occurs when the CB model alone is used.

INTRODUCTION

From full spectral modelling of surface waves, considerable progress[1,2,3] has been made in simulating radar signatures of the Rip-like sub-mesoscale feature that was observed during the First High Resolution Remote Sensing[4] (HI-RES-1) experiment. During this experiment, a meandering, sinusoidally-shaped region of large radar return, ranging between 10 and 15 dB in relative variation, was observed at a current convergence front[4,6], located at the boundary between Shelf water and the Gulf Stream near Cape Hatteras, NC. Quantitative agreement was obtained for the magnitude of this signature, based on two, independent models of the surface currents[1,2,3], and application of full-spectrum wave-current interaction calculations of surface wave spectra and the composite backscatter (CB) model, but only after additional effects from wave-breaking (WB) were included in an approximate manner through an improved version of the radar backscatter model. These earlier studies involved one-dimensional models of the surface currents, which were represented either as a simple current convergence[1] or as a

current convergence in the presence of a shear[2,3]. As a consequence, the resulting estimates are applicable to regions where the effects of changes in the direction of the Rip are not pronounced. In the calculations presented in this paper, a more sophisticated, sinusoidally-varying, 2-dimensional model of the surface current structure is used that provides a more reliable representation of the underlying structure in regions where the direction of the Rip changes. Very good agreement with experiment is obtained for the magnitude of the signature (~11-17 dB) across and within the Rip, but only when the effects of wave breaking are included. In particular, it is found that when the CB model is used alone, within the Rip, the cross-section varies over a considerably larger range (6-16 dB) than is observed experimentally and also exhibits a non-physical dependence on look-angle that was not observed. When WB effects are included, these deficiencies are eliminated, and it is found that the location of maximal and minimal cross-section, and the manner in which cross-section varies within the meander all agree well with the experimentally derived imagery.

METHOD

Previous simulations[1-3] of RCS of the HI-RES-1 Rip feature have been based on wave-current interaction calculations of wave height spectra F , as a function of two-dimensional wave-vector \mathbf{k} , at locations \mathbf{r} on the ocean surface. In these calculations, F is derived from the intrinsic angular wave frequency $\omega_o(k) (\equiv (gk + T/\rho k^3)^{1/2})$, $k \equiv |\mathbf{k}|$, $\rho = \text{density of sea water}$, $T \equiv \text{surface tension}$ and wave action density $N(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{k}, t) \equiv \omega_o(\mathbf{k})/k$ F , using either one (y-dependent) component[1] V , or both (U , and V) components[2,3] of the current, with the important simplifying assumption that the only spatial dependence in the currents occur in one direction: $V \equiv V(y)$, and[2,3] $U \equiv U(y)$. From these calculations of F , simulations of RCS were derived from the CB model, and two extensions of the CB model that incorporate WB effects.

Because these currents only included a dependence on y , it was not possible from these calculations to infer information about the behavior of the RCS in regions where strong spatial variation in the Rip occurs in both the x - and y -directions. To investigate this point, we have employed a different model, in which $V=0$, and $U=U(x,y)$ is modelled from

$$U(x, y) = -\frac{\delta U}{2} \tanh\left[\frac{\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_o \sin\left(\frac{2\pi y}{\lambda}\right)}{\delta x}\right]. \quad \mathbf{1}$$

Here, the values for $\delta U=6$ m/s and $\delta x=30$ m are used to mimic the convergence, observed [4] during HI-RES-1, that was used previously[1-3], while the values $x_0=300$ m, and $\lambda=1500$ m were inferred radar imagery[4,5,6]. Using this current model, N is derived from

$$\nabla_{\mathbf{k}} \omega \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} N - \mathbf{k}_x \left[\frac{\partial U}{\partial x} \frac{\partial N}{\partial \mathbf{k}_x} + \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \frac{\partial N}{\partial \mathbf{k}_y} \right] = -\beta \frac{N}{N_o} (N - N_o),$$

where $\omega=\omega_0 + \mathbf{k}_x U$, and β and N_o , respectively, are the Plant wind growth rate and Bjerkaas-Riedel equilibrium wave action that were used previously [1-3].

As before[2,3], RCS values were determined from F , using the CB model, avoiding the small slope approximation[3] that was used in [1]. WB effects were investigated, using the LWBC approach[2,3], in which the RCS is derived probabilistically, by combining the CB model RCS (suitably weighted so that it applies in locations where breaking does not occur) with an approximate Feature model of a breaking wave, using the probabilities $P(\mathbf{r})$ and $(1-P(\mathbf{r}))$ for wave-breaking to occur and not occur at \mathbf{r} . Specifically, the RCS is derived from

$$\sigma_{tot}^{sp} = (1 - P(\mathbf{r}))\sigma_{CS}^{sp} + P(\mathbf{r})\sigma_{WB}^{sp}, \quad 2$$

where $P(\mathbf{r})$ and σ_{wb}^{sp} , respectively, are inferred from crest acceleration Ω and wave-height variance values that are derived from F . To determine $P(\mathbf{r})$, it is necessary to establish a critical value $\Omega=\Omega_c$ of the crest acceleration, beyond which breaking is assumed to occur with 100% certainty. As in [2,3], this was accomplished by performing a number of calculations involving different values of Ω_c and finding a particular value that maximizes the variation in RCS across the Rip. The resulting value $\Omega_c = 0.4$ g is very close to the value ($\Omega_c = 0.38$ g) that was obtained previously [2,3] and agrees with independently measured values that have been obtained in wave-tank and field measurements. Additional details of the LWBC procedure are presented in [3].

RESULTS

Fig. 1 shows plots of the RCS with (Fig. 1B) and without (Fig. 1A) WB when the radar is pointed across the Rip. The signature (S) of the Rip appears as the meandering sinusoidally-varying region of large RCS-variation found in the center of each plot. The largest RCS-variations (~15-18 dB) are found in the locally vertical regions of large variation located in the "cusp-like" positions (marked by arrows) within the S in both plots. The smallest variations in RCS within the S in each case are found in the "non-cusp-like" regions (also marked by arrows). In the non-WB case (Fig. 1A), this minimal RCS-variation (within the non-cusp-like

Fig. 1: Simulated RCS values, looking across Rip, without (A) and with (B) Wave-Breaking, in dB (as marked) relative to the minimum value associated with each plot. The schematic of the airplane is used to indicate the flight path in each plot. "Cusp-like" ("non-cusp-like") regions (marked by arrows) refer to regions where the signature is strongly (weakly) dependent on 2-dimensional variations in position within the Rip.

portion of the S), relative to the minimal RCS value (found far from S) is ~6 dB; while in the cusp-like region, the comparable RCS-variation is 16 dB. Although experimentally[6], in comparable "cusp-like" regions, large ~15 dB variations in RCS were observed, variations in RCS of ~10 dB were observed in the "non-cusp-like" regions. As a result, when the CB model is used alone, a considerably larger range of variation (~10 dB) in RCS is obtained within the Rip than was observed. Considerable improvement (as can be seen in Fig. 1B) is obtained when the WB effect is

included. For this case, we find that in the “cusp-like” and

Fig. 2: Simulated RCS values, looking along Rip, without (A) and with (B) Wave-Breaking, in dB (as marked) relative to the minimum value of the RCS obtained in each plot. The schematic of the airplane is used to indicate the flight path in each plot.

“non-cusp-like” regions, respectively, the RCS varies by ~17 and ~12 dB. Thus, by including 2-dimensionally-varying currents, it is found that when the radar is pointed across the rip, significant (~15-18 dB) variations in RCS are obtained in the “cusp-like” regions of the Rip, regardless of whether or not WB effects are included, and this variation in RCS is significantly larger than the comparable variation that is obtained in “non-cusp-like” regions. Both of these trends agree with experimental observation. However, without WB, the range (~6-16 dB) of variation in RCS-values within the S is considerably larger than is observed experimentally. By incorporating WB, it is found that this deficiency is eliminated and quantitative agreement is obtained.

The presence of WB effects does not significantly increase the magnitude of the simulated signatures in the cusp-like regions. This is somewhat surprising since in the earlier 1-dimensional calculations, when WB is not included, the signature is underpredicted by 5 dB. In fact, in the non-cusp regions, the signature is underpredicted by 5 dB in the CB case, suggesting that the signature in these regions more closely approximates the comparable 1-dimensional results. A possible reason for the enhanced return in the cusp region is that the shear (defined by the gradient of U in the y-direction) behaves differently there than in the non-cusp region.

WB effects are also found to be important in our ability to simulate the look angle dependence. In particular, it is found that without WB effects, the RCS exhibits a sensitivity with respect to changes in look-angle that was not found experimentally, while when WB effects are included, this deficiency is eliminated. This effect is illustrated in Figs. 2 (A,B), where simulated plots of RCS are shown when the radar is pointed along the Rip (i.e., perpendicularly to the dominant current convergence). From this plot, it is seen that the signature effectively disappears in simulations that do not incorporate the WB effect, while for cases in which WB is included, the signature closely resembles the comparable signature that is obtained when the radar is pointed across the Rip.

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